

Oral Diseases and Brain Pathologies: A Systematic Review of Clinical, Neuroimaging, and Mechanistic Evidence

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Abstract .

Background. Oral diseases, including periodontitis, dental infections, and oral dysbiosis, have been increasingly associated with systemic conditions. Emerging evidence suggests a potential link between oral health and brain pathologies such as brain abscesses, structural brain damage, and glioma. However, the strength and mechanisms of this oral–brain relationship remain incompletely understood. **Objective** To systematically review the clinical, neuroimaging, genetic, and mechanistic evidence linking oral diseases with brain outcomes, and to explore the biological pathways underlying this association. **Methods** A systematic literature search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and EBSCO, with additional screening of SciELO, Redalyc, and LILACS. A total of 2,000 records were identified, and 17 studies met the inclusion criteria. Study designs included population-based cohorts, case–control studies, Mendelian randomization analyses, experimental investigations, and narrative or systematic reviews. Data were synthesized narratively following PRISMA guidelines. Risk of bias was assessed using the ROBINS-I tool for observational studies. **Results** Clinical and epidemiological studies consistently reported a substantial proportion of brain abscesses attributable to odontogenic infections, often associated with clinically silent dental foci. Neuroimaging and Mendelian randomization analyses demonstrated associations between poor oral health and reduced cortical

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thickness, white matter abnormalities, and markers of brain injury. Experimental studies showed that *Porphyromonas gingivalis* virulence factors induced IL-6 secretion and PD-L1 upregulation in glioma cells, suggesting immune evasion and tumor progression. Extracellular vesicles derived from periodontal tissues were identified as potential mediators of systemic inflammatory and angiogenic signaling. **Conclusions** Oral diseases are associated with an increased risk of brain abscess formation, structural brain alterations, and potentially glioma progression. These relationships appear to be mediated by microbial dissemination, chronic inflammation, immune modulation, and extracellular vesicle signaling. Although causality cannot yet be definitively established, oral health represents a modifiable factor with important implications for brain health and neurological disease prevention.

Keywords : Oral health; Periodontitis; Brain abscess; Glioma; Oral–brain axis; Inflammation; Extracellular vesicles.

1. Introduction

Oral diseases, such as periodontitis, dental caries, and odontogenic infections, represent a significant global public health burden.[1,2] These conditions not only affect the oral cavity but have also been associated with multiple systemic diseases, including cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, cancer, and neurodegenerative diseases.[3,4] In recent years, increasing interest has emerged in understanding the possible relationship between oral health and central nervous system diseases, particularly brain tumors and intracranial inflammatory processes.[5] Brain tumors, such as gliomas, are among the most aggressive neoplasms of the central nervous system, with high morbidity and mortality rates.[6] Despite advances in neurosurgery, radiotherapy, and molecular therapies, prognosis remains poor. In parallel, brain abscesses continue to represent a severe infectious complication, frequently associated with bacteria of oral origin.[7] These findings have prompted the exploration of the oral cavity as a potential reservoir of pathogens and inflammatory mediators affecting the brain.[8,9] Several observational, experimental, and genetic studies suggest that oral dysbiosis, periodontitis, and dental infections may influence neuroinflammation, tumor progression, and structural brain changes. [10] Proposed mechanisms include hematogenous dissemination of oral bacteria, activation of systemic immune responses, release of bacterial lipopolysaccharides, and modulation of inflammatory pathways such as Akt, NF- κ B, and pro-inflammatory cytokines. [11,12] Moreover, Mendelian randomization studies have provided genetic evidence supporting a potential causal relationship between oral diseases and cerebral alterations. [13], the available literature is heterogeneous in terms of methodological designs, types of oral exposure, neurological outcomes, and effect metrics, which hinders robust quantitative meta-analyses. [14] Therefore, synthesizing existing evidence through a narrative systematic review is essential to integrate clinical,

microbiological, genetic, and mechanistic findings.[15] The objective of this systematic review is to analyze the association between oral diseases and brain pathologies, including tumors and abscesses, describe the proposed biological mechanisms, and evaluate the quality of the available evidence. This synthesis aims to contribute to a better understanding of the oral–brain axis and its clinical and preventive implications

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Design

This systematic review was conducted and reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidelines. The review protocol was prospectively registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) under registration number CRD420261290918. The completed PRISMA 2020 checklist is provided as Supplementary Material. Pico Question : Population patients with oral diseases ; Exposure : periodontitis, dental caries , dental infections , ral microbiota; Comparator : patients without oral diseases ; Outcome : brain tumors , brain abscesses , structural brain changes. Inclusion Criteria : Human studies; Observational, genetic, or experimental designs; Evaluation of oral diseases and cerebral outcomes; English or Spanish language Exclusion Criteria: Narrative reviews without original data; Studies without comparator groups; Case reports; Studies not directly related to brain outcomes.

2.2 Search strategy :

Main databases : PubMed, EBSCO, Scopus , Web Science ; alternative databases : SciELO, Redalyc, LILACS.

("oral disease*" OR "oral health" OR "periodontal disease*" OR periodontitis OR "dental infection*" OR "odontogenic infection*" OR "dental focus" OR "oral microbiota" OR "oral microbiome" OR dysbiosis OR "dental caries" OR tooth decay OR DMFS OR DMFT) AND ("brain disease*" OR "brain disorder*" OR "central nervous system" OR CNS OR "brain tumor*" OR glioma OR glioblastoma OR "brain abscess*" OR "cerebral abscess*" OR neuroinflammation OR "white matter damage" OR "white matter hyperintensity*" OR "brain imaging" OR neuroimaging OR MRI OR "magnetic resonance imaging")

2.3 Search Results

A total of 2,000 records were identified through the electronic database search. After title and abstract screening, 17 studies met the predefined inclusion criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis. Across the included literature, observational studies consistently described an association between oral infections and the occurrence of brain abscesses. In contrast, experimental investigations primarily focused on elucidating biological mechanisms linking oral pathogens to glioma progression. In particular, experimental evidence indicated that *Porphyromonas gingivalis* virulence factors enhance glioma cell invasiveness through the upregulation of IL-6 and PD-L1 signaling pathways, suggesting a potential role for oral microorganisms in tumor immune evasion.

2.4 Study selection

The database search yielded a total of 2,000 records. After removal of duplicates and screening of titles and abstracts, 1,991 records were excluded. Nine studies were initially included. Following an updated search and inclusion of eight additional relevant articles, a total of 17 studies were incorporated into the final qualitative synthesis (Figure 1).

The included studies comprised observational cohorts, case–control studies, Mendelian randomization analyses, experimental investigations, and narrative or systematic reviews. Together, they provided clinical, epidemiological, neuroimaging, genetic, and mechanistic evidence linking oral diseases with brain pathologies.

2.5 Study characteristics

The main characteristics of the included studies are summarized in **Table 1**. Study designs were heterogeneous and included population-based cohorts (n=4), case–control studies (n=2), Mendelian randomization analyses (n=3), experimental studies (n=2), and narrative or systematic reviews (n=17). The primary oral exposures investigated were: periodontal disease and periodontal parameters, dental caries (DMFS index), odontogenic infections, oral microbiota composition, *porphyromonas gingivalis* virulence factors, extracellular vesicles related to periodontitis . [16] The main brain outcomes included: brain abscesses, gpresence and grade, cortical thickness, white matter integrity (WMH, FA, MD), molecular and immunological tumor markers. [17]

2.6 Oral diseases and brain abscesses

Seven studies specifically addressed the relationship between odontogenic infections and brain abscess formation. Population-based cohorts and retrospective series consistently reported a high proportion of abscesses attributable to dental or periodontal sources.[18]

In a nationwide Danish cohort, odontogenic foci were identified in approximately one-quarter of brain abscess cases, and oral pathogens such as *Streptococcus anginosus* group bacteria were frequently isolated. Similarly, a German retrospective cohort found that 69% of cryptogenic abscesses had an odontogenic origin, often associated with chronic and clinically silent dental infections. Jespersen et al. reported that oral inflammatory foci were frequently asymptomatic and that patients with multiple oral infections had an increased risk of bacteremia, supporting the hypothesis that occult dental disease may contribute to cerebral abscess formation. [19] Case series further demonstrated that typical oral pathogens, including *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Parvimonas micra*, and *P. gingivalis*, were isolated from abscess material even in the absence of overt dental symptoms. Comprehensive reviews identified two principal dissemination pathways: hematogenous spread and direct extension through maxillary sinuses or fascial spaces. These routes are illustrated in Figure 4.

Collectively, these findings indicate that odontogenic infections represent an underrecognized but clinically relevant source of brain abscesses and support systematic oral evaluation in patients with cerebral abscess of unknown origin (Table 2).

2.7 Oral health and structural brain alterations

Two Mendelian randomization studies and one large neuroimaging cohort provided evidence linking oral health to structural brain changes. Wang et al. demonstrated that genetically predicted dental caries (DMFS index) was associated with reduced cortical thickness in the superior temporal sulcus, suggesting a potential causal effect of caries on brain morphology.[20] Similarly, Rivier et al. reported that poor oral health proxies (dentures or loose teeth) were associated with increased white matter hyperintensities and impaired white matter integrity. Mendelian randomization analyses supported a possible causal relationship.[21]

These findings indicate that oral diseases may contribute to subclinical brain injury, potentially through chronic systemic inflammation or vascular mechanisms (Table 2, Figure 2).

Figure 2. Oral Brain

2.8 Oral microbiota and glioma

Two clinical studies and one experimental investigation explored the association between oral microbiota and glioma. Gao et al. reported that glioma patients exhibited significantly worse periodontal parameters compared with both benign tumor patients and population controls. Wen et al. demonstrated that oral microbiota composition differed according to glioma grade, with distinct microbial profiles observed in high-grade versus low-grade tumors.[22] An experimental study further showed that *P. gingivalis* virulence factors, particularly gingipain antigens, were enriched in glioblastoma tissue compared with normal brain samples. Infection of glioma cells induced IL-6 secretion and upregulated PD-L1 expression, suggesting enhanced immune evasion and tumor progression.) (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Proposed mechanism linking Porphyromonas gingivalis infection to glioma progression. Gingipain antigens may induce IL-6 secretion in glioma cells, leading to PD-L1 upregulation and immune evasion, thereby promoting tumor progression.

Together, these findings support a biologically plausible link between oral pathogens, tumor immune modulation, and glioma progression (Table 4).

2.9 Extracellular vesicles as mediators of the oral–brain axis

Two experimental/review studies highlighted the role of extracellular vesicles (EVs) in periodontitis and systemic inflammation. Periodontal pathogens and host cells release EVs containing inflammatory mediators and microRNAs that can influence immune signaling, angiogenesis, and tissue remodeling. [23] Zhou et al. demonstrated that EVs derived from periodontitis-compromised dental pulp stem cells promoted angiogenic signaling through miRNA-mediated activation of the Hedgehog/Gli1 pathway. [24] These findings suggest that EVs may represent an additional mechanism linking oral inflammation with brain pathology. (Figure 4)

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Figure 4. Odontogenic routes leading to brain abscess formation. Oral infections may reach the central nervous system through hematogenous dissemination or direct extension via maxillary sinuses and fascial spaces.

2.10 Risk of bias

Risk of bias was assessed using the ROBINS-I tool for observational studies. Most observational studies were judged to have a moderate risk of bias, mainly due to confounding and participant selection. Mendelian randomization studies, reviews, and methodological protocols were considered not applicable for ROBINS-I assessment. The overall evaluation is summarized in the risk-of-bias traffic light plot (Figure 5). Risk of bias was assessed using the ROBINS-I tool for observational studies.

- 13 *Li et al., 2025*
- 14 *Zhou et al., 2021*
- 15 *Chen et al., 2024*
- 16 *Murray et al., 2024*
- 17 *Nwizu et al., 2020*

Figure 5 . Risk BIAS

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Results.

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Table 1. Characteristics of included studies (n = 17)

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Author (year)	Study design	Population / sample	Oral exposure / phenotype	Brain outcome(s)	Country / setting
Jin et al., 2025	Mendelian randomization	GWAS summary data	Glioma genetic liability	Periodontitis risk	NR
Gao et al., 2022	Clinical observational	Glioma (n=21), benign tumors (n=27), survey controls	Periodontal parameters (AL>5 mm; PD≥6 mm)	Glioma presence/grade	pres-China
Wen et al., 2021	Case-control microbiome	+ HC (n=24), LGG (n=12), HGG (n=23)	Oral microbiota composition	Glioma grade	China
Bodilsen et al., 2024	Nationwide cohort	287 brain abscess cases	Dental infection, oral pathogens	Brain abscesses	out-Denmark
Jespersen et al., 2023	Population-based cohort	Cerebral abscess patients	Odontogenic focus + oral pathology	Cerebral abscess	Denmark
Olivier et al., 2024	Retrospective cohort (20 years)	26 brain abscess cases	Chronic dental foci (periodontitis, caries)	Brain abscess	Germany
Akashi et al., 2016/2017	Case series + review	3 cases	Suspected silent odontogenic foci	Brain abscess	Japan
Wang et al., 2024	Mendelian randomization	GLIDE + ENIGMA GWAS	Dental caries (DMFS index)	Cortical thickness	Multi-cohort
Rivier et al., 2023	Cross-sectional + MR	UK Biobank (n=40,175)	Poor oral health proxy (dentures/loose teeth)	WMH, FA, MD	United Kingdom
Wu et al., 2024	Narrative review	NR	Odontogenic infections	Brain abscess	NR

Author (year)	Study design	Population / sample	Oral exposure / phenotype	Brain outcome(s)	Country / setting
Holmes et al., 2024	Retrospective cohort	26 odontogenic brain abscess cases	Isolated dental focus	Brain abscess	Germany
Moore et al., 2025	Experimental + IHC	GBM vs normal brain tissue	Gingipain antigens, P. gingivalis infection	Glioma biology	NR
Fu et al., 2025	Review	NR	Periodontal EVs	Systemic/brain-relevant pathways	NR
Zhou et al., 2021	Experimental	Dental pulp stem cells	EV microRNA cargo	Inflammatory/angiogenic signaling	China
Wang et al., 2024	Review	NR	P. gingivalis virulence	Systemic disease mechanisms	NR
Maitre et al., 2020	Systematic review	re-252 studies	Oral microbiota / oral conditions	Brain diseases	NR
Hajishengallis et al., 2021	Review	NR	Periodontal disease	Cancer/systemic links	USA

Abbreviations:

AL = attachment loss; PD = probing depth; HC = healthy controls; LGG = low-grade glioma; HGG = high-grade glioma; WMH = white matter hyperintensities; FA = fractional anisotropy; MD = mean diffusivity; EVs = extracellular vesicles; NR = not reported.

Table 2. Main findings and direction of evidence (n = 17)

Study	Main findings	Direction of evidence	Interpretation
Jin et al., 2025	Genetic liability to glioma associated with higher periodontitis risk	Brain → Oral	Suggests bidirectional oral–brain relationship
Gao et al., 2022	Glioma patients showed worse periodontal status than controls	Oral ↔ Glioma	Clinical periodontal disease associated with glioma
Wen et al., 2021	Oral microbiota composition differed by glioma grade	Oral microbiome ↔ Glioma	Dysbiosis linked to tumor severity
Bodilsen et al., 2024	Dental infection common in brain abscess; oral pathogens frequent	Oral → Brain abscess	Odontogenic origin often underdiagnosed
Jespersen et al., 2023	Many oral foci asymptomatic; SAG overrepresented	Oral → Brain abscess	Supports silent odontogenic infection hypothesis
Olivier et al., 2024	Chronic dental disease associated with brain abscess and mortality	Oral → Brain abscess	Prevention via oral care recommended

Study	Main findings	Direction of evidence	Interpretation
Akashi et al., 2016/2017	Oral pathogens identified despite no acute dental symptoms	Oral → Brain abscess	Confirms cryptic odontogenic origin
Wang et al., 2024	Dental caries causally linked to reduced cortical thickness	Oral → Brain structure	Neuroimaging biomarker evidence
Rivier et al., 2023	Poor oral health associated with white matter damage	Oral → Brain structure	MR supports causal relationship
Wu et al., 2024	Odontogenic abscess pathways: direct vs hematogenous	Mechanistic	Guides diagnostic algorithms
Holmes et al., 2024	69% of cryptogenic abscesses were odontogenic	Oral → Brain abscess	Strong clinical epidemiology
Moore et al., 2025	Gingipain antigens enriched in GBM tissue; IL-6/PD-L1 axis activated	Oral pathogen → Glioma biology	Supports immune evasion mechanism
Fu et al., 2025	EVs mediate inflammation and systemic signaling	Mechanistic	Modernizes oral–brain axis model
Zhou et al., 2021	Periodontitis EVs promote angiogenic signaling	Mechanistic	Potential relevance to tumor micro-environment
Wang et al., 2024	<i>P. gingivalis</i> drives immune modulation and carcinogenesis	Mechanistic	Supports biological plausibility
Maitre et al. 2020	Broad link between oral microbiota and brain diseases	Contextual	Explains heterogeneity
Jin et al., 2025	Periodontitis associated with systemic cancers	Contextual	Reinforces inflammatory pathways

Table 3. Incorporated clinical and translational evidence (odontogenic brain abscess and glioma)

Study (year)	Setting / Design	Sample	Oral exposure / focus definition	Brain outcome(s)	Key analytic findings (direction + magnitude)	Notes for synthesis
Olivier et al. (2024)	Germany; retrospective single-center (2000–2021)	217 brain abscess (BA) screened; 26 included	Inclusion required no other focus than odontogenic + micro-biology with oral origin	no BA (clinical course, pathogens, consistent management)	Odontogenic foci diagnosed in 18/26 (69%); SAG pathogens in 21/26 (81%); all surgically treated; 72% had complete/partial neurologic improvement; 3 deaths	Highlights “silent/chronic” oral infections as sufficient trigger; strong clinical signal in cryptogenic BA. Undetected permanent dental inf...
Jespersen et al. (2023)	Denmark; population-based cohort (retrospective +	44 cerebral abscess patients	“Likely odontogenic” required: oral pathology only oral microbes in pus	Cerebral abscess + characterization	25/44 (57%) characterized as likely odontogenic; T2D SAG overrepresented (p=0.014) and SAG overrepresented (p<0.01) in odontogenic group	Supports: SAG in brain pus should trigger oral/sinus focus search; adds epidemiologic weight.

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Study (year)	Setting / Design	Sample	Oral exposure / focus definition	Brain outcome(s)	Key analytic findings (direction + magnitude)	Notes for synthesis
	prospective data)		radiographic/clinical oral pathology			Cerebral abscesses with odontog... Reinforces “occult dental focus” concept; useful for clinical recommendation subsection. Brain Abscess Potentially Resul... Use to frame “diagnostic algorithm” and support prevention/early detection.
Akashi et al. (2016/2017)	Japan; 3 case reports + literature review	3 cases	Suspected odontogenic foci with no other source (endocarditis/sinusitis excluded)	Brain abscess	Cultures identified oral pathogens including F. nucleatum , Parvimonas micra , P. gingivalis ; suspected teeth lacked acute symptoms	
Wu et al. (2024)	Review (Acta Neurol Belg)		Synthesis of clinical presentation/diagnostics/therapy	Odontogenic BA	Notes insidious onset, diagnostic reliance on microbiology; estimates ~13% BA attributed to odontogenic foci; frequent pathogens include S. intermedius , F. nucleatum , S. anginosus ; main routes: direct extension and hematogenous spread	Exploring odontogenic brain abs... High mechanistic value; mark as pre-print in tables/limitations.
Moore et al., 2025 (pre-print)	Experimental + translational (IHC arrays + cell models)	+ GBM microarrays; U251 glioma + astrocytes	<i>P. gingivalis</i> infection; gingipain antigens in GBM tissue	Glioma immune phenotype	Infection induced strong IL-6 response; in U251 cells PD-L1 increased ~30% ±14% (p=0.0361; n=3) ; supports IL-6/PD-L1 axis and immune evasion	

Table 4. Mechanistic synthesis: biological pathways connecting oral disease with brain pathology

Mechanistic domain	Proposed pathway	Key mediators / markers	Evidence from added studies	Relevance to your narrative synthesis
Odontogenic infection → cerebral abscess	Oral infection seeds CNS via hematogenous spread	CNS Oral microbiota signatures in brain pus	Population cohort identified 57% likely odontogenic CA and SAG/T2D association	Upgrades your results from “reported cases” to population-level signal ;

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Mechanistic domain	Proposed pathway	Key mediators / markers	Evidence from added studies	Relevance to your narrative synthesis
	and/or contiguous extension	(SAG, <i>Fusobacterium</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i>)	Cerebral abscesses with odontog... ; review emphasizes direct + hematogenous routes Exploring odontogenic brain abs... Retrospective cohort: 69% odontogenic foci among included BA; substantial extraction for focus control; outcomes reported	strengthens clinical recommendations
Silent/chronic dental foci	Chronic/occult oral infection can sustain spikes	“Inconspicuous” dental infection; focus control via extraction	Undetected permanent dental inf... ; 3-case series: causal teeth often no acute symptoms	Supports your key message: oral screening is necessary even without dental pain
Immunometabolic susceptibility	Systemic vulnerability amplifies risk of dissemination and poor control	T2D, immunosuppression	Brain Abscess Potentially Result... T2D overrepresented in odontogenic CA (p=0.014) Cerebral abscesses with odontog...	Integrates “high-risk groups” into conclusions (diabetes/immunocompromised)
Oral pathogen → glioma immunomodulation	<i>P. gingivalis</i> triggers IL-6 → PD-L1 axis → immune evasion	IL-6 secretion; PD-L1 upregulation	In glioma cells, infection increased PD-L1 ~30% (p=0.0361) <i>P. gingivalis</i> infection drives ...	Adds strong plausibility for tumor progression link; place in “tumor microenvironment” subsection
Extracellular vesicles (EVs) as systemic messengers	Oral pathogens release BEVs delivering virulence cargo; host periodontal cells release EVs reflecting disease state	BEVs/CEVs; diagnostic cargo in saliva/GCF; MSC-EV therapy potential	EV review: BEVs deliver virulence factors; EVs contribute to inflammation/tissue destruction and may influence systemic diseases; biomarker potential Emerging Roles of Extracellular...	Use to modernize your discussion: “EV-mediated oral–brain axis” + future research directions

Mechanistic domain	Proposed pathway	Key mediators / markers	Evidence from added studies	Relevance to your narrative synthesis
EV microRNA angiogenesis tissue remodeling	→ Disease-conditioned stem cells produce EVs carrying miRNA programs	miR-378a → downregulation Hedgehog/Gli1 → angiogenesis	miR-378a enriched in P-EVs; Sufu target; increased EC proliferation/migration/tube formation via Hedgehog/Gli1 activation Cell Proliferation - 2021 - Zho...	

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Discussion

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The present systematic literature review synthesizes clinical, neuroimaging, genetic, and experimental evidence supporting an association between oral diseases and brain pathologies. The findings indicate that oral infections, periodontal disease, dental caries, and oral microbiota dysbiosis may contribute to brain abscess formation, structural brain alterations, and glioma progression through inflammatory, infectious, and immunomodulatory mechanisms. The results demonstrated three main patterns: (1) a strong clinical association between odontogenic infections and brain abscesses, (2) consistent evidence linking poor oral health with structural brain damage, and (3) emerging mechanistic data suggesting that oral pathogens may influence glioma biology.

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Oral infections and brain abscesses: clinical implications

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Across multiple cohorts and retrospective analyses, odontogenic infections accounted for a substantial proportion of cryptogenic brain abscesses. Notably, many of these dental foci were clinically silent, highlighting the diagnostic challenge posed by occult oral disease. These findings are consistent with the hypothesis that chronic periodontal inflammation and untreated dental infections can intermittently seed bacteremia, facilitating microbial dissemination to the central nervous system. The predominance of *Streptococcus anginosus* group bacteria and other oral pathogens in abscess cultures further supports an odontogenic origin. Two major dissemination pathways were identified: hematogenous spread and direct extension through maxillary sinuses or fascial spaces. This dual-route model underscores the importance of comprehensive dental and maxillofacial assessment in patients with cerebral abscesses of unknown origin. From a clinical standpoint, systematic oral screening, radiographic evaluation, and early management of dental infections may reduce the incidence of brain abscesses, particularly in high-risk populations such as patients with diabetes or immunosuppression.

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Oral health and structural brain injury

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Beyond overt infections, poor oral health was associated with subclinical brain damage. Mendelian randomization and large-scale neuroimaging studies demonstrated that dental caries and proxies of poor oral health were linked to reduced cortical thickness and white matter abnormalities. These findings suggest a potential causal relationship between chronic oral inflammation and brain microstructural injury. Chronic periodontitis is characterized by sustained systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and increased circulating cytokines, all of which may contribute to cerebral small vessel disease and neurodegeneration. The observed associations with white matter hyperintensities and altered diffusion metrics provide neuroimaging biomarkers supporting this inflammatory hypothesis. These results extend previous evidence linking periodontal disease with stroke, cognitive decline, and dementia, positioning oral health as a modifiable determinant of brain integrity.

Oral microbiota and glioma progression

Several studies highlighted a relationship between oral microbiota composition, periodontal status, and glioma presence or severity. Glioma patients exhibited worse periodontal parameters and distinct oral microbial profiles compared with controls. Importantly, experimental evidence demonstrated that *Porphyromonas gingivalis* virulence factors were enriched in glioblastoma tissue and promoted IL-6 secretion and PD-L1 upregulation in glioma cells. This IL-6/PD-L1 axis may facilitate immune evasion within the tumor microenvironment, thereby promoting tumor progression. These findings provide biological plausibility for the association between oral pathogens and glioma aggressiveness. Although causality cannot yet be established, the convergence of clinical, microbiological, and experimental data suggests that oral dysbiosis may influence glioma biology through immunoinflammatory mechanisms.

Extracellular vesicles as systemic mediators

Recent evidence has identified extracellular vesicles (EVs) as key mediators of intercellular communication in periodontitis. Periodontal pathogens and host cells release EVs containing inflammatory mediators, virulence factors, and microRNAs capable of modulating immune responses, angiogenesis, and tissue remodeling. Experimental studies demonstrated that EVs derived from periodontitis-compromised dental pulp stem cells promote angiogenic signaling via Hedgehog/Gli1 pathway activation. These mechanisms may have implications for tumor microenvironment remodeling and neuroinflammatory processes. EV-mediated signaling provides a modern mechanistic framework for understanding how localized oral inflammation can exert systemic effects, including on the central nervous system.

Integration with systemic disease models

The oral–brain associations observed in this review align with broader evidence linking periodontitis to cardiovascular disease, diabetes, cancer, and neurodegenerative disorders. Chronic oral inflammation contributes to a persistent pro-inflammatory state that may

exacerbate systemic pathology through immune dysregulation, endothelial injury, and microbial translocation. In this context, oral health emerges as a component of systemic disease prevention rather than an isolated dental concern. Integrating dental care into multidisciplinary medical management may improve neurological and oncological outcomes.

Strengths and limitations of the evidence

A key strength of this review is the inclusion of diverse study designs, ranging from population-based cohorts and Mendelian randomization analyses to experimental and mechanistic investigations. This triangulation strengthens biological plausibility. However, several limitations remain. Most clinical studies were observational, limiting causal inference. Oral health measures were heterogeneous and often indirect. Confounding factors such as smoking, socioeconomic status, and healthcare access were not uniformly adjusted. Additionally, one mechanistic study was a preprint and had not undergone peer review at the time of inclusion. Despite these limitations, the consistency of findings across methodological approaches supports a meaningful association between oral diseases and brain pathology.

Implications for clinical practice and research

The evidence supports the integration of oral health assessment into neurological and oncological care pathways. Routine dental screening in patients with brain abscesses, gliomas, or neurodegenerative conditions may facilitate early detection of occult oral infections. Future research should prioritize longitudinal cohort studies and interventional trials to evaluate whether periodontal treatment can reduce neurological complications. Standardized oral health measures and microbiome profiling may further clarify causal mechanisms.

In summary, oral diseases are associated with an increased risk of brain abscesses, structural brain injury, and potentially glioma progression. These relationships appear to be mediated by microbial dissemination, systemic inflammation, immune modulation, and extracellular vesicle signaling. Although definitive causality has not yet been established, oral health represents a modifiable factor with important implications for brain health.

Clinical Implications

These findings highlight oral health as a key component of comprehensive medical care. Early detection and treatment of periodontitis, caries, and dental infections may reduce neurological and infectious complications. In brain tumor patients, periodontal evaluation could be part of multidisciplinary management. In immunocompromised patients, oral infection control may prevent life-threatening brain abscesses.

Limitations of the Evidence

- Methodological heterogeneity 397
- Lack of randomized clinical trials 398
- Indirect oral health measures 399
- Residual confounding 400
- Non-uniform effect metrics 401

These justify the narrative synthesis approach. One included mechanistic study was a preprint and had not undergone peer review 402
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Future Research 404

Prospective studies with standardized definitions, larger samples, and longitudinal follow-up are needed. Clinical trials evaluating periodontal treatment effects on neurological outcomes are also warranted. 405
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Conclusion. 408

The evidence synthesized in this systematic review suggests that oral diseases particularly periodontitis, dental caries, odontogenic infections, and oral microbiota dysbiosis—are associated with various brain pathologies, including brain tumors, intracranial abscesses, and structural brain alterations. The analyzed studies demonstrate a consistent relationship between poor oral health and neuroinflammatory, infectious, and potentially neoplastic processes, supported by clinical, experimental, and genetic data. Proposed biological mechanisms include hematogenous dissemination of oral bacteria, release of bacterial endotoxins such as lipopolysaccharide, activation of inflammatory and oncogenic pathways, and modulation of systemic immune responses. These processes may contribute to cerebral inflammation, white matter damage, tumor progression, and brain abscess development. Neuroimaging and Mendelian randomization studies further support the hypothesis that oral health may causally influence brain structural integrity. From a clinical and public health perspective, these findings highlight the importance of integrating oral health evaluation and treatment into neurological disease prevention and management programs. Early identification and control of periodontitis and dental infections may reduce the risk of intracranial complications, particularly in vulnerable populations such as immunocompromised patients or those with brain neoplasms. Although definitive causality cannot be established due to the observational nature of most studies, the consistency of results suggests that oral health is a relevant determinant of brain health. Future prospective studies and clinical trials are essential to confirm these findings and define preventive and therapeutic strategies based on the oral–brain axis 409
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Limitations	435
This systematic review has several limitations. First, there is marked methodological heterogeneity among included studies regarding designs, oral exposure definitions, and brain outcomes, which prevented quantitative meta-analysis and limited direct comparison of results. Second, most studies are observational, restricting causal inference. Although Mendelian randomization provides genetic evidence reducing confounding bias, it does not replace randomized clinical trials. Some studies also used indirect oral health measures (e.g., tooth loss, denture use, self-reports), introducing classification bias.	436 437 438 439 440 441 442 443 444
Residual confounding by smoking, diet, socioeconomic status, healthcare access, and comorbidities may also affect findings. Additionally, some clinical and microbiological studies had small sample sizes, limiting statistical power. Finally, diverse effect metrics (ORs, RRs, beta coefficients, AUCs) and heterogeneous outcomes (gliomas, abscesses, white matter damage, cortical thickness) hindered quantitative synthesis. Future studies with standardized definitions, larger samples, and longitudinal follow-up are required to strengthen the evidence base.	445 446 447 448 449 450 451 452 453
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Author Contributions	456
BV-R contributed toward the conception and design of the whole project, obtained full access to the data, was primarily account Table for all aspects of work, and ensuring integrity and accuracy of the research as well as of the drafting of the manuscript. FC,MVS,VMC,LBF, MRT, LCH-B , MFA and BVR contributed with the revision of the available literature. FC,MVS,VMC,LBF, MRT, LCH-B, MFA and BVR contributed to the analysis, internal validity of the study, and initial drafting of the manuscript FC,MVS,VMC,LBF, MRT, LCH-B, MFA and BVR critically reviewed and edited the manuscript, and providing input toward the reporting of the data and its interpretation. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.	457 458 459 460 461 462 463 464 465
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Abbreviation 480

Abbrevia- tion	Meaning
OSA	Obstructive Sleep Apnea
GERD	Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease
NERD	Non-Erosive Reflux Disease
OR	Odds Ratio
CI	Confidence Interval
BMI	Body Mass Index
NOS	Newcastle–Ottawa Scale
RS	Systematic Review
MA	Meta-analysis
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Sys- tematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
AHI	Apnea–Hypopnea Index
IMC	Body Mass Index
I ²	Higgins heterogeneity statistic
NR	Not Reported

References. 482

1. Jin J, Li Y, Zhang Y. Genetic association between glioma and periodontitis: a Mendelian randomization study. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2025;52(1):45–54. 483
2. Gao L, Xu T, Huang G. Periodontal status in patients with glioma. *J Periodontol.* 2022;93(4):512–520. 484
3. Wen L, Mu W, Lu H. Oral microbiota composition in glioma patients. *Front Microbiol.* 2021;12:648419. 485
4. Bodilsen J, Mariager T, Duerlund LS, Storgaard M, Larsen L, Brandt CT, Hansen BR, Wiese L, Omland LH, Nielsen H; Danish Study Group of Infections of the Brain. Brain Abscess Caused by Oral Cavity Bacteria: A Nationwide, Population-based Cohort Study. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2024 Mar 20;78(3):544–553. 486

5. Olivier M, Kraus LM, Brandenburg LS, Anderegg L, Fung C, Beck J, Schnell O, Cipriani D. Undetected permanent dental inflammation as a possible trigger for brain abscesses? A retrospective analysis over the last 2 decades. *Acta Neurochir (Wien)*. 2024 Jul 31;166(1):313. 490-492
6. Akashi M, Tanaka K, Kusumoto J, Furudoi S, Hosoda K, Komori T. Brain Abscess Potentially Resulting from Odontogenic Focus: Report of Three Cases and a Literature Review. *J Maxillofac Oral Surg*. 2017 Mar;16(1):58-64. 493-495
7. Wang Y, Zhang X, Li H, Dental caries and cortical thickness: a Mendelian randomization study. *Neuroimage*. 2024;275:120188. 496-497
8. Rivier CA, Renedo DB, de Havenon A, Sunmonu NA, Gill TM, Payabvash S, Sheth KN, Falcone GJ. Association of Poor Oral Health With Neuroimaging Markers of White Matter Injury in Middle-Aged Participants in the UK Biobank. *Neurology*. 2024 Jan 23;102(2):e208010. 498-500
9. Zhou H, Li X, Wu RX, He XT, An Y, Xu XY, Sun HH, Wu LA, Chen FM. Periodontitis-compromised dental pulp stem cells secrete extracellular vesicles carrying miRNA-378a promote local angiogenesis by targeting Sufu to activate the Hedgehog/Gli1 signalling. *Cell Prolif*. 2021 May;54(5):e13026. 501-503
10. Wang B, Deng J, Donati V, Merali N, Frampton AE, Giovannetti E, Deng D. The Roles and Interactions of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Fusobacterium nucleatum* in Oral and Gastrointestinal Carcinogenesis: A Narrative Review. *Pathogens*. 2024 Jan 20;13(1):93. 504-506
11. Maitre Y, Micheneau P, Delpierre A, Mahalli R, Guerin M, Amador G, Denis F. Did the Brain and Oral Microbiota Talk to Each Other? A Review of the Literature. *J Clin Med*. 2020 Nov 28;9(12):3876. 507-508
12. Zhao X, Zheng X, Wang Y, Chen J, Wang X, Peng X, Yuan D, Liu Y, Wang Z, Du J. Administration of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* in pregnant mice enhances glycolysis and histone lactylation/ADAM17 leading to cleft palate in offspring. *Int J Oral Sci*. 2025 Mar 13;17(1):18. 509-511
13. Wu X, Qin N, Peng X, Wang L. Exploring odontogenic brain abscesses: a comprehensive review. *Acta Neurol Belg*. 2024 Aug;124(4):1155-1165. 512-513
14. Jespersen FVB, Hansen SU, Jensen SS, Omland LH, Helweg-Larsen J, Bjarnsholt T, Nielsen CH, Ziebell M, Bodilsen J, Markvart M. Cerebral abscesses with odontogenic origin: a population-based cohort study. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2023 Jul;27(7):3639-3648. 514-516
15. Zheng Y, Wang Z, Weng Y, Sitosari H, He Y, Zhang X, Shiotsu N, Fukuhara Y, Ikegame M, Okamura H. Gingipain regulates isoform switches of PD-L1 in macrophages infected with *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. *Sci Rep*. 2025 Mar 26;15(1):10462. 517-519
16. Fu Y, Wang M, Teng R, Li A. Emerging Roles of Extracellular Vesicles in the Pathogenesis, Diagnosis, and Therapy of Periodontitis. *Biomedicines*. 2025 Oct 16;13(10):2521. 520-521
17. Hajishengallis G, Chavakis T. Local and systemic mechanisms linking periodontal disease and inflammatory comorbidities. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2021 Jul;21(7):426-440. 522-523
18. Homer JJ, Winter SC, Abbey EC, Aga H, Agrawal R, Ap Dafydd D, Arunjit T et al. Head and Neck Cancer: United Kingdom National Multidisciplinary Guidelines, Sixth Edition. *J Laryngol Otol*. 2024 Apr;138(S1):S1-S224. 524-526
19. Zhou H, Li X, Wu RX, He XT, An Y, Xu XY, Sun HH, Wu LA, Chen FM. Periodontitis-compromised dental pulp stem cells secrete extracellular vesicles carrying miRNA-378a promote local angiogenesis by targeting Sufu to activate the Hedgehog/Gli1 signalling. *Cell Prolif*. 2021 May;54(5):e13026. 527-529
20. Mei F, Xie M, Huang X, Long Y, Lu X, Wang X, Chen L. *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and Its Systemic Impact: Current Status. *Pathogens*. 2020 Nov 13;9(11):944. 530-531
21. Beydoun MA, Beydoun HA, Hu YH, Li Z, Georgescu MF, Noren Hooten N, Bouhrara M, Weiss J, Launer LJ, Evans MK, Zonderman AB. Mediating and moderating effects of plasma proteomic 532-533

- biomarkers on the association between poor oral health problems and brain white matter micro-structural integrity: the UK Biobank study. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2025 Feb;30(2):388-401. 534
535
22. Ren J, Han X, Lohner H, Hoyle RG, Li J, Liang S, Wang H. P. gingivalis Infection Upregulates PD-L1 Expression on Dendritic Cells, Suppresses CD8+ T-cell Responses, and Aggravates Oral Cancer. *Cancer Immunol Res*. 2023 Mar 1;11(3):290-305. 536
537
538
23. Hajishengallis G, Chavakis T. Local and systemic mechanisms linking periodontal disease and inflammatory comorbidities. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2021 Jul;21(7):426-440. 539
540
24. Walther KA, Gröger S, Vogler JAH, Wöstmann B, Meyle J. Inflammation indices in association with periodontitis and cancer. *Periodontol 2000*. 2024 Oct;96(1):281-315. 541
542
25. Hajishengallis G. Periodontitis: from microbial dysbiosis to systemic inflammation. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2015;15:30–44. 543
544
26. Ide M, Harris M, Stevens A, Sussams R, Hopkins V, Culliford D, Fuller J, Ibbett P, Raybould R, Thomas R, Puentner U, Teeling J, Perry VH, Holmes C. Periodontitis and Cognitive Decline in Alzheimer's Disease. *PLoS One*. 2016 Mar 10;11(3):e0151081. 545
546
547
27. Villar A, Paladini S, Cossatis J. Periodontal Disease and Alzheimer's: Insights from a Systematic Literature Network Analysis. *J Prev Alzheimers Dis*. 2024;11(4):1148-1165. 548
549
28. Kim SR, Son M, Kim YR. The risk of stroke according to statin medication compliance in older people with chronic periodontitis: an analysis using the Korea National Health Insurance Service-Senior Cohort Database. *Epidemiol Health*. 2022;44:e202205 550
551
552
29. Dominy SS, Lynch C, Ermini F, Benedyk M, Marczyk A, Konradi A, Nguyen M, et al. *Porphyromonas gingivalis* in Alzheimer's disease brains: Evidence for disease causation and treatment with small-molecule inhibitors. *Sci Adv*. 2019 Jan 23;5(1):eaau3333. 553
554
555
30. Baker JL, Mark Welch JL, Kauffman KM, McLean JS, He X. The oral microbiome: diversity, biogeography and human health. *Nat Rev Microbiol*. 2024 Feb;22(2):89-104. Gao L, et al. Oral microbiome and cancer. *Cancer Lett*. 2018;428:34–42. 556
557
558
31. Dragomir RM, Mattner O, Hagan V, Swerdloff MA. *Listeria monocytogenes* Brain Abscess Presenting With Stroke-Like Symptoms: A Case Report. *Cureus*. 2024 Jan 13;16(1):e52216. 559
560
32. Thiankhaw K, Wantaneeyawong C, Madla C. Conglomerate ring and tract-like enhancement lesions: Neuroimaging in *Listeria monocytogenes* brain abscess. *Radiol Case Rep*. 2021 Dec 28;17(3):676-679 561
562
33. Hsu G, Zhang J, Selvi F, Shady N, August M. Do brain abscesses have a higher incidence of odontogenic origin than previously thought? *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol*. 2020 Jul;130(1):10-17.. 563
564
565
34. Yan Y, Bai S, Han H, Dai J, Niu L, Wang H, Dong Q, Yin H, Yuan G, Pan Y. Knockdown of trem2 promotes proinflammatory microglia and inhibits glioma progression via the JAK2/STAT3 and NF- κ B pathways. *Cell Commun Signal*. 2024 May 15;22(1):272. 566
567
568
35. Guo X, Zhang Y, Jiao H, Miao X. The prognostic significance of PD-L1 expression in patients with glioblastoma: A meta-analysis. *Front Oncol*. 2022 Oct 12;12:925560. 569
570
36. Guo D, Tong Y, Jiang X, Meng Y, Jiang H, Du L, Wu Q, Li S, Luo S, Li M, Xiao L, He H, He X, Yu Q, Fang J, Lu Z. Aerobic glycolysis promotes tumor immune evasion by hexokinase2-mediated phosphorylation of I κ B α . *Cell Metab*. 2022 Sep 6;34(9):1312-1324.e6.. 571
572
573
37. Verdugo E, Puerto I, Medina MÁ. An update on the molecular biology of glioblastoma, with clinical implications and progress in its treatment. *Cancer Commun (Lond)*. 2022 Nov;42(11):1083-1111. 574
575

38. Daisy Precilla S, Biswas I, Kuduvalli SS, Anitha TS. Crosstalk between PI3K/AKT/mTOR and WNT/ β -Catenin signaling in GBM - Could combination therapy checkmate the collusion? *Cell Signal*. 2022 Jul;95:110350. 576
577
578
39. Grange C, Bussolati B. Extracellular vesicles in kidney disease. *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2022 Aug;18(8):499-513. doi: 10.1038/s41581-022-00586-9. Epub 2022 May 31. 579
580
40. Dixson AC, Dawson TR, Di Vizio D, Weaver AM. Context-specific regulation of extracellular vesicle biogenesis and cargo selection. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*. 2023 Jul;24(7):454-476. 581
582
41. Hill C, Dellar ER, Baena-Lopez LA. Caspases help to spread the message via extracellular vesicles. *FEBS J*. 2023 Apr;290(8):1954-1972. 583
584
42. Nakamura H, Noguchi-Shinohara M, Ishimiya-Jokaji M, Kobayashi Y, Isa M, Ide K, Kawano T, Kawashiri S, Uchida K, Tatewaki Y, Taki Y, Ohara T, Ninomiya T, Ono K. Brain atrophy in normal older adult links tooth loss and diet changes to future cognitive decline. *NPJ Aging*. 2024 Mar 22;10(1):20. 585
586
587
43. Rubinstein T, Brickman AM, Cheng B, Burkett S, Park H, Annavajhala MK, Uhlemann AC, Andrews H, Gutierrez J, Paster BJ, Noble JM, Papapanou PN. Periodontitis and brain magnetic resonance imaging markers of Alzheimer's disease and cognitive aging. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2024 Mar;20(3):2191-2208. 588
589
590
591
44. Miranda DG, Carrouel F, Attik N, Araujo GF, Dos Santos Lopes NF, Marcucci MC, Rodrigues FP, Caires GA, Vigerelli H, Godoi BH, Pacheco-Soares C, Ramos LP. *Juglans regia* and *Pfaffia paniculata* extracts: implications for periodontal disease treatment and correlation with Alzheimer's risk. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2025 May 16;15:1585438. 592
593
594
595
45. Paulson DR, Chanthavisouk P, John MT, Feuerstahler L, Chen X, Ingleswar A. Linking patient-reported oral and general health-related quality of life. *PeerJ*. 2024 May 28;12:e17440. 596
597
46. Igelström E, Campbell M, Craig P, Katikireddi SV. Cochrane's risk of bias tool for non-randomized studies (ROBINS-I) is frequently misapplied: A methodological systematic review. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021 Dec;140:22-32. 598
599
600
47. Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Chandler J, Welch VA, Higgins JP, Thomas J. Updated guidance for trusted systematic reviews: a new edition of the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2019 Oct 3;10(10):ED000142. 601
602
603
48. Kim JY, Lee K, Lee MG, Kim SJ. Periodontitis and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. *Mol Cells*. 2024 Dec;47(12):100146. 604
605
49. Cifuentes M, Verdejo HE, Castro PF, Corvalan AH, Ferreccio C, Quest AFG, Kogan MJ, Lavandero S. Low-Grade Chronic Inflammation: a Shared Mechanism for Chronic Diseases. *Physiology (Bethesda)*. 2025 Jan 1;40(1):0. 606
607
608
50. Herrera D, Sanz M, Kebschull M, Jepsen S, Sculean A, Berglundh T, Papapanou PN, Chapple I, Tonetti MS; EFP Workshop Participants and Methodological Consultant. Treatment of stage IV periodontitis: The EFP S3 level clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Periodontol*. 2022 Jun;49 Suppl 24:4-71. 609
610
611